

B-Z Chemical Oscillation in Perchloric Acid Medium with Gallic Acid as the Substrate

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Manuscript received 17 November 1994, revised 31 March 1995, accepted 22 May 1995

B-Z oscillating chemical reaction has been studied using gallic acid as the substrate in a new acid medium, namely, perchloric acid medium, both visually and potentiometrically side by side by batch method. Various concentrations of perchloric acid have been used and both uncatalysed and catalysed reactions using ferroin have been studied. The reaction has also been followed in presence of different amounts of acetone. The resulting changes in oscillation parameters have been analysed in each case. Studies at different temperatures have led to the determination of apparent values of E_a , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger .

Belousov-Zhabotinskii reaction¹ is perhaps the most widely studied oscillating chemical reaction. Various organic and inorganic substances have been used as single or mixed substrates. Gallic acid²⁻⁵ has been a very popular organic substrate as the colour changes (orange to green in presence of ferroin) are very prominent and demonstration experiments are very easy. Previous studies have used sulphuric acid medium for B-Z systems containing gallic acid. In the present studies perchloric acid has been used as a substitute for sulphuric acid.

Both visual and potentiometric studies have been simultaneously made. The changes in oscillation parameters like induction period, number of oscillations, total time of oscillation and oscillation period on changing concentration of perchloric acid and concentration of acetone have been noted. A comparison of the oscillation parameters in the uncatalysed system and catalysed system using ferroin (which also acts as a redox indicator) has been made. From the oscillation studies at several temperatures, the apparent energy of activation (E_a), the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and the entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) have been evaluated.

Results and Discussion

The traces in Figs. 1-4 show the plot of potential of the system vs time. The potential of the system increased whenever a green colour appeared in the system. Figs. 1 and 2 are for different concentrations of perchloric acid and

Figs. 3 and 4 for different concentrations of acetone. The oscillation parameters and the kinetic parameters evaluated therefrom have been shown in Tables 1-4

Fig 1 Potential oscillation in GA KBrO₃ ferroin system at different concn of HClO₄ (a) 2.5, (b) 2.25 and (c) 2.0 M

TABLE 1—OSCILLATORY CHARACTERISTICS OF B-Z SYSTEM IN DIFFERENT CONCN OF PERCHLORIC ACID

GA = 0.032 M, KBrO₃ = 0.1 M, Ferroin = 1.23 × 10⁻⁴ M

HClO ₄ Concn M	Induction period (s)		No. of oscillation		Total time of oscillation (s)		3rd oscillation period (s)		4th oscillation period (s)	
	Visual	Pot	Visual	Pot	Visual	Pot	Visual	Pot	Visual	Pot
2.50	*	*	6	7	*	120	*	*	*	*
2.25	141	144	36	36	600	624	*	8	*	7
2.00	245	240	63	63	1260	1260	*	8	*	9
1.75	555	560	73	74	1970	1980	26	24	27	25
1.50	212	288	6	6	600	600	93	96	106	105
1.25	471	479	3	3	745	744	*	*	*	*

*Not clear or not detectable.

Fig 2 Potential oscillation in GA KBrO_3 -ferriin system at different concn of HClO_4 (d) 1.75, (e) 1.5 and (f) 1.25 M

Table 1 shows the oscillation parameters obtained visually and potentiometrically when the concentration of perchloric acid was changed and Figs. 1 and 2 show the corresponding potential traces. With decreasing concentration of HClO_4 the number of oscillations increases at first and then decreases, whereas the induction period and the total time of oscillation increase, then decrease and increase again. The time period of 3rd and 4th oscillation increases as the concentration of HClO_4 is decreased. The last observation is comparable to that in H_2SO_4 medium³.

Fig 3 Potential oscillation in GA KBrO_3 -ferriin system in presence of acetone (a) 0 and (b) 5%

Fig 4 Potential oscillation in GA- KBrO_3 -ferriin system in presence of acetone (c) 10, (d) 15 and (e) 20%

Table 2 shows results of the observations when gallic acid and acetone were used as a mixed substrate. A run was also given in absence of acetone. The potential traces are shown in Figs. 3 and 4. The induction period and oscillation period (3rd and 4th) decrease whereas the number of oscillations and total time of oscillation increase in presence of acetone. With increasing acetone concentration, the induction period, total time of oscillation and time period decrease, whereas the number of oscillations remains more or less same. The same trend was observed in our earlier work⁵ in H_2SO_4 medium.

In Table 3, results of the observations in catalysed and uncatalysed systems have been recorded. At high concentration of HClO_4 , no oscillation was observed for the uncatalysed system. At lower concentrations, the number of oscillations and total time of oscillation are lower in uncatalysed system. The induction periods in catalysed and uncatalysed systems are virtually the same.

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ACETONE ON B-Z REACTION WITH GALLIC ACID AS ORGANIC SUBSTRATE

 GA = 0.021 M, KBrO₃ = 0.066 M, HClO₄ = 1.66 M, Ferroin = 8.3 × 10⁻⁵ M

Acetone % (v/v)	Induction period (s)		No. of oscillation		Total time of oscillation (s)		3rd oscillation period (s)		4th oscillation period (s)	
	visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.
0	522	528	5	5	1 021	1 020	237	238	341	348
5	423	424	14	14	2 017	2 000	—	216	215	206
10	280	276	10	10	301	312	30	34	31	32
15	227	226	12	12	174	176	18	20	11	12
20	176	176	12	12	126	124	08	08	10	08

TABLE 3—OSCILLATION STUDY IN CATALYSED AND UNCATALYSED B-Z SYSTEM

 GA = 0.032 M, KBrO₃ = 0.1 M, Ferroin = 1.23 × 10⁻⁴ M

HClO ₄ Concn. M	Induction period (s)				No. of oscillation				Total time of oscillation (s)				2nd oscillation period (s)			
	Catalysed		Uncatalysed		Catalysed		Uncatalysed		Catalysed		Uncatalysed		Catalysed		Uncatalysed	
	Vis	Pot	Visual	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.	Vis.	Pot.
2.25	133	144	*	*	29	28	*	*	500	500	*	*	7	7	*	*
2.00	178	180	*	*	70	72	*	*	1 500	1 560	*	*	12	12	*	*
1.75	555	560	*	*	73	74	*	*	1 970	1 980	*	*	29	26	*	*
1.50	280	280	280	288	5	5	4	4	412	410	265	270	92	96	86	94
1.25	420	420	429	430	3	3	2	2	443	444	211	206	248	248	*	*

*Not clear or not detectable.

TABLE 4—STUDY OF B-Z OSCILLATION AT DIFFERENT TEMPERATURES

 GA = 0.032 M, HClO₄ = 1.75 M, KBrO₃ = 0.1 M, Ferroin = 1.23 × 10⁻⁴ M

Temp. K	Induction period (s)		No. of oscillation		Total time of oscillation (s)		3rd oscillation period (s)		4th oscillation period (s)	
	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.	Visual	Pot.
292.5	965	972	38	56	3 840	3 672	100	98	98	92
304	396	396	51	51	1 346	1 349	39	40	24	24
308	153	145	46	—	925	840	10	—	13	—
311	96	96	56	48	900	576	07	07	05	05
313	87	84	25	37	336	432	14	10	08	10
E_a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	87.06				96.319				92.82	
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	109.60				99.93				89.278	
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-674.62				-656.24				-557.56	

The effect of temperature on the system is shown in Table 4. The induction period and total time of oscillation decrease with increase in temperature. The change in number of oscillations is, however, not regular. The time period decreases with increase in temperature but it increases when the temperature is increased further. The results are comparable with our earlier work⁴ in H₂SO₄ medium.

Considering chemical oscillation as a monomolecular^{4,6} process and using the reciprocal of the time period at initial concentrations as a first order rate constant (K), the apparent activation energy (E_a) of the oscillation has been evaluated (using Arrhenius equation, $K = A \exp(-E_a/RT)$) from the slope of the straight-line plot of $\log K$ vs $1/T$. For this purpose, several 'times' namely, the oscillation period, total time of oscillation and induction period were considered. Further, the enthalpy of activation (ΔH^\ddagger) and entropy of activation (ΔS^\ddagger) were evaluated from Eyring equation,

$$K = e \frac{kT}{h} \exp(T\Delta S^\ddagger - \Delta H^\ddagger)/RT$$

and its logarithmic form,

$$\log \frac{K}{T} = \log \left(\frac{ek}{h} \right) + \frac{\Delta S^\ddagger}{2.303 R} - \frac{\Delta H^\ddagger}{2.303 RT}$$

A plot of $\log K/T$ vs $1/T$ gave a straight-line, the slope and intercept of which gave ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger respectively. In this case several 'times' were considered in a similar manner. The values of E_a , ΔH^\ddagger and ΔS^\ddagger obtained on using different 'times' (Table 4) are comparable among themselves. The values are somewhat different from those obtained in H₂SO₄ medium⁴.

From Tables 1–4, it is seen that there are some variations in data obtained from visual and potentiometric observations. Moreover, the oscillatory behaviour is dependent on the speed of the magnetic stirrer. Though the oscillations are sharp in general and can be easily detected visually, they are not always so during the early period or later period of oscillation. Naturally some error creeps in. The oscillation in electric potential goes on for a very long period in some cases, but as the amplitudes are small towards the end, total time of oscillation or total number of oscillation becomes uncertain to some extent.

The FKN mechanism⁷ for metal ion catalysed BZ reactions and OKN mechanism⁷ for uncatalysed BZ systems have been successfully used to explain the main aspects of these reactions. In the present investigation, it is likely that the reaction involves the oxidation of gallic acid by KBrO_3 to its quinonoid form⁸ (Q) which is converted to quinone radical by Br^\bullet or BrO_2^\bullet and ultimately bromogallic acid is formed.

In presence of ferroin catalyst, the usual reactions take place and in absence of external catalyst, the quinonoid form (Q) acts as the effective catalyst.

It has been reported⁸ that prior to onset of oscillation an almost equally large release of energy followed by a mild endothermic event takes place in presence and absence of ferroin. This can perhaps explain the observation made by us that the induction period does not depend on whether the external catalyst has been used or not. The observation that the number of oscillations is much less in uncatalysed reaction is probably due to the fact that ferroin helps the system to cross a threshold barrier quickly whereas Q is less efficient in this respect.

Experimental

To a weighed amount of gallic acid, perchloric acid of desired strength and a few drops of ferroin were added and the reaction was triggered by adding a solution of potassium bromate. All the solutions were so prepared and mixed that the concentrations (shown in Tables 1-4) were the concentrations in medium at the start. Nothing was

added during the run of the oscillation so as to obtain a closed system in the thermodynamic sense. The reaction mixture was moderately stirred at a fixed rate. The oscillations were recorded visually from the sharp colour changes from orange to green. For potentiometric measurement, a bright platinum electrode was used in the reaction vessel which was connected to a saturated calomel electrode (reference electrode) through an ammonium nitrate salt bridge. The potential of the system was recorded with the help of a $x-t$ strip chart recorder.

The system, however, was not a homogeneous one because a white precipitate was formed in the system presumably due to formation of potassium perchlorate.

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